

ULUGBEK HAMDAM'S "FATHER" NOVEL

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Annotation: the novels of Ulugbek Hamdam, warmly received in Uzbek literary criticism, have always been the center of attention. His novel "father" is also a work that clearly demonstrates the skill of a writer. In the novel, the writer revealed through the characters the qualities of pride, dishonesty inherent in the Uzbek nation, Uzbek guys.

Keywords: skilled writer, opposite of nation, Uzbek father, hero figure, symbolism

Ulugbek Hamdam, who entered Uzbek literature with his new heroes, always surprises the reader. The author's novel "Ota" on national and original themes is one of the works that reflects the image of the real Uzbek nation. It can be understood from the theme of the work that the Uzbek family, its lifestyle, life, and the father who considers himself responsible for this life, is the father of a real Uzbek.

The novel begins first with the happy moments of hearts thirsty for love, and then with the hot pains of the hearth of war. The struggle for life, the willingness to do anything to save life, or the battle, which shows how insignificant and priceless the human soul is, shakes the heart. While reading the work, if you admire Polat, who was born as an Uzbek, his honor, his conscience, his care as a father, you feel so sorry for his pride and being a victim of deception. The skill of the writer is that he sometimes makes the reader happy and sometimes torments. Also, the writer pays special attention to the names of the characters in the novel

and assigns a task to each name. Each name seems to express symbolism. Or as if the hero's name determines his fate. "Polat and Yogdu's joy could not fit not only in the hearts, but also in the worlds... When brother Otkir and sister Oychechak had no offspring other than Polat... They named the baby Joy" [1.78.] . In fact, each character has a character that matches the meaning of their name. At the same time, the meaning of the names is also related to their fate.

Polat is the only son of Oychechak, conscientious, noble, who waited a long time for his child to be born, Yodu's trust, Sevinch's friend (he has a strong will like steel). Oychechak - Polat's mother, a believer in all kinds of secrets, a supporter of Otkur's brother (a woman who shines like a moon for the family). Otkir brother - a simple man who married with Aychechak, a simple man who trusted his wife, a person who made war sharp (returned alive from the war). Yogdu - Polat's heart, love, hope for life, a woman who quarreled with Erboy and married after quarreling (she brightened Polat's life, she was the source of his life). Joy is an angel who entered the life of her parents as Joy, the reason for her father's life (a girl who brought joy and happiness to her family). The author of the novel chose the names of these characters in such a way that each name fulfilled its role in the lives of the characters and the events of the work. Erboy is a constant threat to the lives of the heroes (he died because he couldn't reach Yoghdu). He was able to bring pain, suffering and torture into Polat's house full of happiness.

The father described in the novel is the pillar of the house, an authoritative person who has a great position in the Uzbek household, and his word is the law. Polat, the hero of the work, like all Uzbek fathers, is a family man. Lives with his dreams, listens to his heart, understands, solves his problems. The world becomes dark when Sevinch is caught in a fire after a terrible incident in his childhood. Especially, the scar left by the fire on Sevinch's face scratches and torments the father's heart every day, forcing him to collide with me inside. She takes her

daughter, who cannot join the children, to school by herself, plays together, in general, lives with her daughter again, grows up with her, goes through everything for her daughter's pleasure. Sevinch, who grew up with his father, finished his studies and started working as a doctor. The father is still the pain of his daughter. Unexpectedly, when he heard that his lifelong companion had a child (before his wedding), Polat completely forgot himself, he forgot that he was Polat. It shows what true fatherhood looks like. Especially after hearing this from Erboy, who has been a hostage to his life, he can't help himself. He stabs to death his happiness, his existence, the only one he raised on his shoulders. After this tragedy, Polat was imprisoned. But he does not regret killing his daughter while in prison. He believes that he did the right thing. Why did he kill his daughter? Out of pain, on purpose, out of deception, or did an unexpected blow confuse him? Of course, from the power of honor!

He did what every Uzbek father can do. The father put his daughter above everything else, brought her up on his shoulders, heard and understood her, but Polat proved that the honor of his Uzbek father is higher than any kind of love. He did not forgive his daughter even later, especially Yogdusi, who was very trusting. Yogdu died when he was released from prison, and there is no one at home. This world condemned Polat to loneliness. Having heard from somewhere that Sevinch has a child, Polat remained indifferent, but at the end of the play he went to his grandson, and when he saw him, he forgot everything. He took her with him. That's how people get used to everything over time. Sometimes it's simple to do things that you say you can't it does. Thus, man is a mysterious, undiscovered ocean of the soul. In spite of everything, he lives, endures, is patient. Polat lived like any other person. His difference from others was that he valued his daughter too much, lived in her life, and because of this, he could not accept the unexpected news and did not forgive. We do not justify or condemn the father in the work. It was his destiny. The writer did not bury the hero of the father in

negative colors, he loved him. The writer wanted to remind young people that we have such honorable, noble, ambitious fathers. He warned of the wrath of the father if he set an example of the father's love for his daughter. The writer, who was able to embody the image of a real Uzbek father in the work, completed the work after burying his hero Polat in positive paint. This is also a sign of the writer's originality. He did not want to arouse hatred in the reader towards his hero.do

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